

#3: Early warning indicators and the risk for cascades of tipping points

Providing an early warning of tipping events is crucial for effective climate adaptation. It is therefore important to test the reliability of existing early warning indicators, investigate indicators of newly discovered tipping points, and develop new methods to deliver more accurate early warnings.

The tipping of one climate element or occurrence of an unprecedented extreme event might cause tipping of another climate element, and might therefore serve as early warning indicator as well. However, the likelihood for occurrence of cascades of tipping points, where the tipping of one element is causing tipping of another one, and the link between extreme climate events and tipping points are not well understood yet.

Action

TipESM will apply existing early warning indicators to tipping points identified in TipESM Earth System Model simulations (see factsheet #2), and develop novel early warning methods to provide more robust warnings. Additionally, TipESM will extend understanding on tipping points cascades by focusing on cascades not investigated before and accounting for feedbacks across Earth system components. TipESM will also advance knowledge on the linkage between extreme climate events and tipping points by scanning existing and the new TipESM simulations for extreme events occurring in advance of tipping events, and investigating how the likelihood of specific extremes triggering tipping events changes with the rate of global warming.

Developing new early warning methods

Existing early warning indicators are based on observing changes in fluctuations of a climate elements, such as the North Atlantic Ocean circulation system. Specifically, a critical increase in the amplitude and a slower recovery of such fluctuations often indicates that a climate element approaches tipping.

TipESM will develop new early warning methods based on two approaches. First, we will focus on temporal fluctuations of a climate element and consider changes in key spatial patterns that may precede a tipping event. These can be, for example, patterns associated with large freshwater exports out of the Arctic, which can lead to large salinity anomalies in the North Atlantic, and could be potential warnings for a collapse of ocean convection in the Labrador Sea or the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). Second, we will explore an approach based on statistical analysis of the time series of a climate element that might be at risk to tip, the so called “autoregressive-moving-average process modelling”. This approach allows for a more robust identification of critical changes in observed temporal fluctuations of a climate element that may indicate an impending tipping of this element.

The newly developed early warning indicators will be applied to Earth System Models to test their reliability. In particular, we will investigate the risk of false positives and how far in advance a tipping point can be predicted.

By focusing on the early warning indicators and risk of tipping points cascades, TipESM will:

- **Develop new early warning methods and study early warning indicators of so far unknown tipping points**
- **Provide guidance for future tipping point observing systems**
- **Improve understanding of potential remote interactions in time and space between different tipping points**
- **Assess the potential for a major extreme event to trigger different tipping elements in the Earth system**

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TipESM - Exploring Tipping Points and Their Impacts Using Earth System Models

TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

Expected impacts of TipESM

The key objectives of the project are to:

- Advance knowledge and solutions in Earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, climate change adaptation, climate services, social science for climate action and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions
- Contribute substantially to key international assessments (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the European Environment Agency)
- Increase the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate and Earth system change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens
- Strengthen the European Research Area with increased knowledge of the risks of crossing climate tipping points

Project partners and associated partners

- Danish Meteorological Institute
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (and their affiliated entities)
- The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
- University of Bergen
- The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
- Barcelona Institute for Global Health
- University of Leeds
- Met Office UK
- University of Reading
- University of Liverpool
- University of Bern
- Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research

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